

An Article on Physiology of Feeling

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Abstract

Emotion can be define as the feeling aspect of consciousness characterized by certain physical arousal, a certain behaviour that reveals the feeling to the outside world and inner awareness of feeling. Firstly we discussed about the central nervous system, how it communicate with the rest of the body.

The peripheral nervous system(PNS) is made up of all the nerves and nervous that are not contained in the brain and spinal cord. This system that allows the brain and spinal cord to communicate with the sensory system of eyes, ears, skin and mouth and allows the brain and spinal cord to control the muscles and glands of the somatic nervous system and the autonomic nervous system.

Keywords Emotion, Behaviour, Physiology, Feeling.

Introduction

The somatic nervous system is made up of all the nerves carrying message from the senses to the central nervous system and all of the nerves carrying message from the central nervous system to the muscles of the body specially the skeletal muscles that allow a person to move their bodies. Somatic nervous system controlled only voluntary muscles nerves coming from the senses are called the sensory pathway & the nervous that make up there nerves are called sensory nervous and the nerves that carry the message to the voluntary muscles are called motor pathway and the nervous in these nerves are the motor nervous.

Objective of study

In this paper author has discussed about the central nervous system, how it communicate with the rest of the body.

Review of Literature

Many books and research papers from online and offline sources has been reviewed for this paper which has been discussed through out the paper.

Analysis

The nervous inside the spinal column are part of the central nervous system. These large groups of nervous near the spinal column make up the autonomic nervous system. The autonomic division control everything else in the body organs, glands and involuntary muscles.

The autonomic nervous system itself is divided in two system the sympathetic division and parasympathetic division.

The sympathetic division of the autonomic nervous system is primarily located on the middle of the spinal column. Running from near the top of the ribcage to the waist area. The sympathetic division is usually called the fight as flight system because it is allows people to deal with all binds of stressful events emotions during these events might be anger (fight) or fear (flight) or even extreme joy or excitement. The heart starts pumping faster and harder , drawing blood away from nonessential organs such as the spin, so at first the person may turn pale and sometime even the brains, so the person might actually faint. Blood needs lots of oxygen before it goes to the muscles, so the lungs work overtime too, and its results person may begin to breathe faster. One site of glands

in particular receives special instructions. The adrenal glands will be stimulated to release certain stress related chemicals hydrocortisone or hormones, into the blood stream. This stress hormone will travel to all parts of the body, but they will only affect certain target organs. Just as a new transmitter fits into a receptor site on a cell, the molecules of the stress hormones fit into receptor sites at the various target organs the heart, muscles and lungs. This further stimulates these organs to work harder.

But not every organ or system will be stimulated by the actuation of the sympathetic division digestion and eliminating waste products are not necessary function when dealing with stressful situations, so these systems tend to be 'shut down' or inhibited. Saliva dries right up, Food that was in the stomach sits there like a lump. Usually, the urge to go to the bathroom will be suppressed, but the bladder may actually empty. The sympathetic division is also going to demand that the body burn a tremendous amount of fuel or blood sugar. due to above reactions of chemicals the heart rate increase, breathing becomes more rapid the pupil dilate & the mouth may become dry .Fear is associate with a decrease in skin temperature where as anger is associated with an increase in skin temperature and a greater increase in blood pressure.

Emotions even work differently depending on which side of the brain is involved. Researchers have found that negative feelings such as sadness, anxiety and depression seem to be a function of primarily the left hemisphere of the brain. But when anxiety & depression were reduced activity level dropped in the left hemisphere and increases in the right hemisphere.

Conclusion

The parasympathetic division is called the eat, drink and rest system. The nervous of this division are located at the top and bottom of the spinal column on either side of the sympathetic division nervous. It might seem as if the parasympathetic division opposite of the sympathetic division but it's a little more complex than that the parasympathetic division job is to restore the body to normal functioning after a stressful situation ends Its slow the heart and breathing constricts the human and reactivates digestion and excretion Signals to the adrenal glands stop, because the parasympathetic division is not connected to adrenal glands. In other words, the parasympathetic division allows the body to put back all energy it burned parasympathetic division is responsible for most of the ordinary day to day bodily functioning. It keeps the heart beat regularly, breathing normal & digestion going and a human spend the greater part of their 24 hours day eating, sleeping, digesting and excreting. So it is the parasympathetic Division that is normally active, so we can say that sympathetic or parasympathetic will determine whether people are aroused or relaxed.

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